

DIDACTIC MECHANISMS OF ENSURING STUDENTS' INFORMATION SECURITY

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Abstract. *The article examines, in the context of globalization of information, in the era of digital technologies, ensuring the information security of the younger generation as a mature individual as a pedagogical problem. Its scientific and theoretical foundations are presented as a pedagogical problem.*

Keywords: *information, security, digital technologies, information security, spiritual space, pedagogical conceptual model.*

Introduction. In terms of ensuring information and psychological security in the world, the presence of aggression in society, manifested in the personal, group and public consciousness of people who are increasingly exposed to aggressive information, occupies a special place. Manifestation of such aggressions greatly harms the mental and spiritual health of citizens and destabilizes the social and political situation in the country. Protection of the individual, group and public consciousness of citizens from the influence of information against the right is the main content of the activities of ensuring the information and psychological security of Uzbekistan, this direction is relatively new and has not yet been sufficiently developed. Formation of informational and psychological security system is extremely urgent nowadays.

Main part. In this regard, when analyzing the literature, it became clear that the problems of ensuring information psychological security in Uzbekistan have not been fully scientifically studied. Currently, there are different approaches to the concept of information and psychological security by foreign scientists and different definitions are given. One such definition is as follows: Information-psychological security is a state of protection of individual, group and mass psychology from various foreign ideas that lead to the destruction of society. It is appropriate to talk about the scientific works of a number of foreign scientists who conducted scientific research on this issue. In scientific works of Russian scholars as I. Panarin, G. Grachev, G. Emelyanov, V. Lepsky, A. Strelsov[1] are devoted to the problem of ensuring informational and psychological security. In their opinion, the main threat to information-psychological security is the mass dissemination of psychological manipulation, or covert psychological coercion. At the same time, they divided the information-psychological security system into 3 main components, which consist of regulatory-legal, organizational and technological parts. The regulatory and legal part consists in the formation of legal norms for identifying threats to information and psychological security and combating them. The organizational part of the information-psychological security system establishes the functional structure of public organizations and state bodies implementing legal norms in this field. The technological part of the system ensures free and safe information exchange between citizens, groups, associations. In addition, according to I.Panarin, information and psychological security is a component of the national security system. That is, he puts forward the opinion that information and psychological security should be covered in a separate section in the state's national security concept, national security strategy and defense doctrine. At the same

time, the object of information-psychological security is: - the information-psychological environment of society; - information resources (spiritual, cultural, national values and other traditions); - the system of forming the political consciousness of the society (worldview, political views, spiritual values, political values); - system of formation of social opinion; - political decision-making system; - the psychology, behavior, etc. of political elites. The purpose of information-psychological security: - protection of citizens, political elites, social groups and the psychology of the population from destructive information-psychological effects; - protection from psychological manipulation of the population by political forces for their own goals; - constant monitoring of the psychological health of the population; - fight against foreign information and psychological expansion. The most important problems of ensuring informational and psychological security include the following: **PERSONAL CONSCIOUSNESS** - in this case, the main threat is the violation of personal abilities due to the purposeful use of means and methods of influencing his subconscious and consciousness without his consent. From this point of view, religious groups promoting bigotry and extremism, which are actively working in Uzbekistan, pose a serious threat to the personal consciousness of citizens. Usually, these actions are aimed at changing the main motivational ideas of the members in a direction that contradicts the standards of social morality, forming stereotypes of anti-social behavior, and dangerous changes in their mentality. Basically, this problem arises due to the instability of the situation in the socio-economic sphere. The field of group consciousness - threats to the group consciousness are violation of the integrity of the interests of the group, creating difficulties in the realization of these interests, discrediting the members of the group, providing information against the right by other groups, social or state organizations in order to exert psychological pressure on them. It is manifested in the form of transfer of the secret. In general, the trend of changes taking place in the world shows that information has become an integral part of our life. Today, in the era of rapidly developing information exchange, teenagers, that is, students, are Internet users all over the world. For minors to access sites on the "Internet" network, it allows them to learn educational content, communicate with classmates and peers, prepare independent lessons, information about school competitions, online olympiads. is expanding the possibility of participation. At this point, it should be noted that our country has measures to prevent such negative factors and a legal base with a strong mechanism in this regard. In addition, on March 26, 2021, the President of our Republic announced "Measures for radical improvement of the system of spiritual and educational affairs". With this document, the priorities of the radical improvement of the system of spiritual and educational work were determined, and by widely promoting the idea of "From national recovery to national progress" based on the principle of goodness and humanity, a healthy worldview and creativity in the society were created nationwide. the tasks of turning it into action, ensuring the integrity of spiritual education in the family, educational organizations and neighborhoods, increasing the culture of the population to use the Internet global information network, strengthening their ideological immunity against ideological and informational attacks. However, at a time when the psychological danger of information is on the rise, destructive ideas influencing the human mind and thinking, studying the possible sources of social conflicts, the psyche of the student, social- It is desirable that political and psychological interests should be studied consistently. Also, in educational institutions, in particular, starting from primary education, the establishment of moral hours and education classes on the use of the Internet for young people in a continuous, continuous manner can also give positive results. At the same time, it is necessary to strengthen the personal

responsibility of students regarding the purposeful use of the Internet, including social networks, and the information culture among them.

1.2. – picture. Pedagogical and conceptual model of Ensuring students' information security

In our children, we should form a generation with confidence in the future, a deep logical thinking, a developed socio-cultural level, a healthy way of life in the heart and mind, a sense of respect for national and national values, in the constant cooperation of the school and parents, and the neighborhood. we need to convey to every family that parents can benefit more through continuous promotion events, debriefing sessions, and trainings.

After all, nano-sized information, which at first glance seems insignificant, directed against the spirituality of the next generation, can turn into a global issue. The organizational pedagogical conceptual model of *ensuring the information security of students*, which reflects all aspects of the processes of ensuring information security of the future generation, subjects and objects of information security, security in the information field and external and internal threats directed at them, is in the following form developed (see Fig. 1.2).

In conclusion, it can be noted that based on the performed analysis, the state, civil society institutions, mass media, internet, family, neighborhood, schools were taken as subjects of information security. Today, in the theory of security, a system of pedagogical measures has been developed that combines the processes related to these areas. Also, the subject of information security, in turn, becomes broad and invisible as internal and external manifestations of information threats. Therefore, preventing information security from becoming spiritual and national security among students is one of the pedagogical problems.

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